

Impact Factor: 5.723

ISSN: 2181-0982

DOI: 10.26739/2181-0982

www.tadqiqot.uz

JNNR

JOURNAL OF NEUROLOGY AND
NEUROSURGERY RESEARCH

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 2

2024

ЖУРНАЛ НЕВРОЛОГИИ И НЕЙРОХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ 5 НОМЕР 2

JOURNAL OF NEUROLOGY AND NEUROSURGERY RESEARCH
VOLUME 5, ISSUE 2

ЖУРНАЛ НЕВРОЛОГИИ И НЕЙРОХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

Бухарский государственный медицинский институт и tadqiqot.uz

Главный редактор:

Ходжиева Дилбар Таджиевна
доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Бухарского государственного медицинского
института. (Узбекистан).
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5883-9533

Зам. главного редактора:

Хайдарова Дилдора Кадиловна
доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Ташкентской медицинской академии.
(Узбекистан).
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-4980-6158

Рецензируемый
научно-практический журнал
“Журнал неврологии
и нейрохирургических исследований”
Публикуется 6 раза в год
№2 (05), 2024
ISSN 2181-0982

Адрес редакции:

ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>;
Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Макет и подготовка к печати
проводились в редакции журнала.

Дизайн - оформления:

Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Журнал зарегистрирован
в Управлении печати и
информации г. Ташкента Рег. №
от 01.07.2020 г.

“Неврологии и нейрохирургических
исследований” 2/2024

Электронная версия

журнала на сайтах:

<https://tadqiqot.uz>
www.bsmi.uz

РЕДАКЦИОННАЯ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Иноятов Амрилло Шодиевич - доктор медицинских наук, профессор, министр здравоохранения. (Узбекистан)

Хайдаров Нодиржон Кадилович – доктор медицинских наук, профессор, ректор Тошкентского государственного стоматологического института. (Узбекистан).

Нуралиев Неккадам Абдуллаевич - доктор медицинских наук, профессор, иммунолог, микробиолог, проректор по научной работе и инновациям Бухарского государственного медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Кариев Гайрат Маратович – доктор медицинских наук, профессор, директор Республиканского научного центра нейрохирургии Узбекистана. (Узбекистан).

Федин Анатолий Иванович - доктор медицинских наук, профессор, заслуженный врач РФ. Российский национальный исследовательский медицинский университет имени Н.И. Пирогова. (Россия).

Маджидова Екутхон Набиевна - доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Ташкентского педиатрического неврологического института. (Узбекистан).

Рахимбаева Гулнора Саттаровна - доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Ташкентской медицинской академии. (Узбекистан).

Джурабекова Азиза Тахировна – доктор медицинских наук, профессор Самаркандского государственного медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Мамадалиев Абдурахмон Маматкулович - доктор медицинских наук, профессор Самаркандского государственного медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Чутко Леонид Семенович - доктор медицинских наук, профессор, руководитель Центра поведенческой неврологии Института мозга человека им. Н.П. Бехтерева. (Россия).

Муратов Фахмитдин Хайритдинович - доктор медицинских наук, профессор Ташкентской медицинской академии. (Узбекистан).

Дьяконова Елена Николаевна - доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Ивановская государственная медицинская академия. (Россия).

Труфанов Евгений Александрович – доктор медицинских наук, профессор Национальной медицинской академии последипломного образования имени П.Л. Шупика. (Россия)

Норов Абдурахмон Убайдуллаевич – доктор медицинских наук, профессор, главный врач Бухарского областного многопрофильного медицинского центра. (Узбекистан)

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаматовна – доктор медицинских наук, профессор Самаркандского государственного медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Азизова Раъно Баходировна - доктор медицинских наук, доцент Ташкентской медицинской академии. (Узбекистан).

Давлатов Салим Сулаймонович - Начальник отдела надзора качества образования, доцент Бухарского государственного медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Саноева Матлюба Жахонкуловна - доктор медицинских наук, доцент Бухарского государственного медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Артыкова Мавлюда Абдурахмановна - доктор медицинских наук, профессор Бухарского государственного медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Уринов Мусо Болтаевич - доктор медицинских наук, доцент Бухарского государственного медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Киличев Ибодулла Абдуллаевич – доктор медицинских наук, профессор Ургенчского филиала Ташкентской медицинской академии. (Узбекистан).

Нарзуллаев Нуриддин Умарович – доктор медицинских наук, доцент Бухарского государственного медицинского института. (Узбекистан).

Рашидова Нилуфар Сафоевна - доктор медицинских наук, доцент Ташкентской медицинской академии. (Узбекистан).

Ганиева Манижа Тимуровна - кандидат медицинских наук, доцент Таджикского государственного медицинского университета (Таджикистан).

Хазраткулов Рустам Бафоевич - руководитель сосудистого отделения Республиканского специализированного научно – практического медицинского центра нейрохирургии, доцент кафедры нейрохирургии Центра развития профессиональной квалификации медицинских работников (Узбекистан).

Нуралиева Хафиза Отаевна - кандидат медицинских наук, доцент Тошкентского фармацевтического института. (Узбекистан).

Исмаилова Раъно Олимджановна – DSc, руководитель научного отдела патологии позвоночника и спинного мозга Республиканского специализированного научно – практического медицинского центра нейрохирургии (Узбекистан).

JOURNAL OF NEUROLOGY AND NEUROSURGICAL RESEARCH

Bukhara State Medical Institute and tadqiqot.uz

Chief Editor:

Khodjueva Dilbar Tadjiyevna

Doctor of medical Sciences, Professor,
Bukhara state medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5883-9533

Deputy editor-in-chief:

Khaydarova Dildora Kadirovna

Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Professor of the Tashkent
Medical Academy. (Uzbekistan).
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-4980-6158

Peer-reviewed scientific and
practical journal "Journal of Neurology
and Neurosurgical Research"
Published 6 times a year
#2 (05), 2024
ISSN 2181-0982

Editorial address:

Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>;
Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Layout and preparation for printing
held in the editorial office of the
journal.

Design – pagemaker:

Khurshid Mirzakhmedov

Journal is registered at the Office of
Press and Information Tashkent city,
Reg. No. July 1, 2020

"Neurology and neurosurgical
research" 2/2024

Electronic version of the

Journal on sites:

www.tadqiqot.uz,
www.bsmi.uz

EDITORIAL TEAM:

Inoyatov Amrillo Shodievich - doctor of medical Sciences, Professor, Minister of health. (Uzbekistan).

Khaydarov Nodirjon Kadirovich - Doctor of Medicine, Professor, Rector of Toshkent State Dental Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Nuraliev Nekkadam Abdullaevich - Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Immunologist, Microbiologist, Vice-Rector for Research and Innovation of the Bukhara State Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Kariev Gayrat Maratovich - Doctor of Medicine, Professor, Director of the Republican Scientific Center for Neurosurgery of Uzbekistan. (Uzbekistan).

Anatoly Ivanovich Fedin - Doctor of Medical Sciences, professor, Honored Doctor of the Russian Federation. Russian National Research Medical University named after N.I. Pirogova. (Russia).

Madjidova Yokutxon Nabieva - Doctor of Medicine, Professor, Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Rakhimbaeva Gulnora Sattarovna - Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, the Tashkent Medical Academy. (Uzbekistan).

Djurabekova Aziza Taxirovna - Doctor of Medicine, Professor, the Samarkand State Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Mamadaliyev Abdurakhmon Mamatkulovich - Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor of the Samarkand State Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Chutko Leonid Semenovich - Doctor of Medicine, Head of the Center for Behavioral Neurology of the Institute of Human Brain named after N.P. Bekhtereva. (Russia).

Muratov Fakhmitdin Khayritdinovich - Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, the Tashkent Medical Academy. (Uzbekistan).

Dyakonova Elena Nikolaevna - Doctor of Medicine, professor of the Ivanovo State Medical Academy. (Russia).

Trufanov Evgeniy Aleksandrovich - Doctor of Medicine, Professor, National Medical Academy of Postgraduate Education named after P.L. Shupika. (Russia).

Norov Abdurakhmon Ubaydullaevich - Doctor of Medicine, professor, Chief Physician of the Bukhara Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center. (Uzbekistan).

Abdullaeva Nargiza Nurmatovna - Doctor of Medicine, professor of the Samarkand State Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Azizova Rano Baxodirovna - doctor of medical Sciences, associate Professor of the Tashkent Medical Academy. (Uzbekistan).

Davlatov Salim Sulaimonovich - Head of the Department of education quality supervision, associate Professor of the Bukhara state medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Sanoeva Matlyuba Jakhonkulovna - Doctor of Medicine, Associate Professor of the Bukhara State Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Artykova Mavlyuda Abdurakhmanovna - Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor of the Bukhara State Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Urinov Muso Boltaevich - Doctor of Medicine, Associate Professor, Bukhara State Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Kilichev Ibdulla Abdullaevich - Doctor of Medicine, professor of the Urgench branch of the Tashkent Medical Academy. (Uzbekistan).

Narzullaev Nuriddin Umarovich - Doctor of Medicine, associate professor of Bukhara State Medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Rashidova Nilufar Safoevna - doctor of medical Sciences, associate Professor of the Tashkent Medical Academy. (Uzbekistan).

Ganieva Manizha Timurovna - Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor, Tajik State Medical University. (Tajikistan).

Hazratkulov Rustam Bafoyevich - head of the vascular department of the Republican specialized scientific and practical medical center of neurosurgery, associate professor of the Department of neurosurgery of the center for the development of professional qualifications of medical workers (Uzbekistan).

Nuralieva Hafiza Otayevna - Candidate of medical Sciences, associate Professor, Toshkent pharmaceutical Institute. (Uzbekistan).

Ismailova Rano Olimdjanovna - Doctor of Medicine, head of the spine department of the Republican specialized scientific and practical medical center of neurosurgery (Uzbekistan).

1. Уринов Мусо Болтаевич, Назарова Жанна Авзаровна, Алиева Нозима Солиевна КОГНИТИВНАЯ ДИНАМИКА ПРИ ЭПИЛЕПСИИ НА ФОНЕ ПРОТИВОСУДОРОЖНОЙ ТЕРАПИИ.....	7
2. Назарова Жанна Авзаровна, Бахадирханов Мухамедшокир Мухамедкабирович ВЛИЯНИЕ КОМПЛЕКСА РЕАБИЛИТАЦИОННЫХ МЕРОПРИЯТИЙ НА ИСХОД ОСТРОГО НАРУШЕНИЯ МОЗГОВОГО КРОВООБРАЩЕНИЯ.....	10
3. Муродова Дилором Субхоновна, Кариев Шухрат Маратович, Полатова Джамиля Шагайратовна СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ДИАГНОСТИКИ И ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ЗЛОКАЧЕСТВЕННЫХ ОПУХОЛЕЙ (ГЛИОМ) ГОЛОВНОГО МОЗГА.....	13
4. Xodjiyeva Dilbar Tadjiyevna, Xayriyeva Muxsina Farxodovna ISHEMIK INSULTDAN KEYINGI KOGNITIV VA MUVOZANAT BUZILISHLARI, ULARNING DIAGNOSTIKASI VA REABILITATSIYASI.....	19
5. Саматов Фаррух Фарходович, Джурабекова Азиза Тохировна, Амонова Захро Кахрамоновна КЛИНИКО-НЕВРОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ НАРУШЕНИЯ У ДЕТЕЙ С БРОНХИАЛЬНОЙ АСТМОЙ.....	22
6. Askarova Fotima Kudratovna TACTICS IN THE MANAGEMENT OF EPILEPSIA BIRTHDAYS (LITERATURE REVIEW).....	27
7. Джурабекова Сурайё Тахировна ЭПИЛЕПСИЯ ПРИ БЕРЕМЕННОСТИ ПРОГНОЗЫ И ЕГО ТЕЧЕНИЯ (ЛИТЕРАТУРНЫЙ ОБЗОР).....	30
8. Mamurova Mavludaxon Mirxamzayeva, Gaybiyev Akmal Axmadjonovich BOLALARDAGI DIABETIK NEVROPATIYALARNING YANGICHA DAVOLASH USULLARI.....	33
9. Гулова Мунисахон Афзаловна МИГРЕНЬ И ГИПЕРТОНИЧЕСКАЯ БОЛЕЗНЬ – СОВРЕМЕННЫЙ ВЗГЛЯД, ПОТЕНЦИАЛ НЕВРОЛОГА (ОБЗОР).....	37
10. Омонова Умида Тулкиновна, Окилжоновна Нигорахон Абдулазизовна, Бахромовна Гавхар Акмаловна КЛИНИКО-НЕВРОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ДЕТЕЙ С НАСЛЕДСТВЕННОЙ СПАСТИЧЕСКОЙ ПАРАПЛЕГИИ ШТРЮМПЕЛЯ В СРАВНИТЕЛЬНОМ АСПЕКТЕ С ДЦП СПАСТИЧЕСКОЙ ДИПЛЕГИИ.....	44
11. Sabirov Jasurbek Oltiboevich, Yuldashev Ravshan Muslimovich, Ismailova Ra'no Olimjanovna ORQA MIYA BO'YIN QISMI INTRAMEDULLYAR O'SMALARINI NEYROFIZIOLOGIK USULLAR YORDAMIDA TASHXISLASH VA DAVOLASH. (ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI).....	49
12. G'aniyev Mirvorisjon Tulqunjon og'li, Yuldashev Ravshan Muslimovich, Kariyev Gayrat Maratovich BOLALARDA ORQA MIYA O'SMALARINI ZAMONAVIY DAVOLASH USULLARI (Adabiyot sharhi).....	52
13. Zulaykho Ravshanbek qizi Egamnazarova, Yulduz Alpisovna Musayeva CHARACTERISTICS OF CLINICAL AND PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL COURSE OF CARDIOEMBOLIC STROKE.....	55
14. Абдурахманова Манзура Абдумуталовна, Туйчибаева Нодира Мираталиевна СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ НА ЮВЕНИЛЬНУЮ МИОКЛОНИЧЕСКУЮ ЭПИЛЕПСИЮ.....	64
15. Зекрияев Нормурод Набиевич, Югай Игорь Александрович, Кариев Гайрат Маратович, Исмаилова Рано Олимжоновна ОСОБЕННОСТИ ОПЕРАТИВНОЙ ТЕХНИКИ ПРИ СЕЛЕКТИВНОЙ ДОРСАЛЬНОЙ РИЗОТОМИИ У ДЕТЕЙ С ДЕТСКИМ ЦЕРЕБРАЛЬНЫМ ПАРАЛИЧОМ.....	69
16. Омонова Умида Тулкиновна, Хаитбаева Наргиза Темуровна ОСОБЕННОСТИ НЕВРОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ РАССТРОЙСТВ ПРИ МУКОВИСЦИДОЗЕ (ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ).....	73
17. Асадуллаев Мақсуд Махмудович, Сохибназаров Нодиржон Ғанижоновиç, Атаниязов Махсуджан Камалиддиновиç, Вахабова Наргиза Мақсудовна, Шамсиева Умида Абдувахидовна ЦЕРЕБРОВАСКУЛЯР КАСАЛЛИКЛАРНИ ЎТКИР ДАВРИДА ДАВОЛАШ ЧОРА-ТАДБИРЛАРИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ.....	76

18. Якубов Жахонгир Баходирович, Кариев Гайрат Маратович, Жавлон Абдуллаевич, Бабаханов Баходир Хуррамович, Эшкувватов Гайрат Эркинович, Бабажанова Лола Бахтияровна ПРЕДРАСПОЛАГАЮЩИЕ ФАКТОРЫ, ЭТИОЛОГИЯ И ПАТОГЕНЕЗ СПОНТАННОЙ НАЗАЛЬНОЙ ЛИКВОРЕИ. ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ.....	81
19. Kamalova Dilafruz Donierovna, Norhujajeva Charoshon Bobir kizi BACK PAIN IN PREGNANCY (LITERATURE REVIEW).....	85
20. Kamalova Malika Ilkhomovna, Rakhmonova Mohigul Shodikulovna EXAM STRESS OF STUDENTS AND METHODS OF ITS OVERCOMING.....	88

BACK PAIN IN PREGNANCY (LITERATURE REVIEW)

<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11288567>

ANNOTATION

Back pain in pregnancy: causes of occurrence, in what diseases it occurs, diagnosis and treatment methods. Back pain is one of the most frequent complaints of pregnant women at appointments at antenatal clinics, especially in late pregnancy. Despite the fact that pregnancy is a natural process, for a woman's body it is a strong stress and brings some discomfort to the life of the future mum, associated with changes in her body and the growth of the baby.

Keywords: back pain, pregnancy, women, hernia, reproductive age

Камалова Дилафруз Донировна
Норхужаева Чаросхон Бобир кизи

Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет

БОЛЬ В СПИНЕ ПРИ БЕРЕМЕННОСТИ (ЛИТЕРАТУРНЫЙ ОБЗОР)

АННОТАЦИЯ

Боль в спине при беременности: причины появления, при каких заболеваниях возникает, диагностика и способы лечения. Боль в спине является одной из самых частых жалоб беременных женщин на приеме в женской консультации, особенно на поздних сроках. Несмотря на то, что беременность – естественный процесс, для организма женщины она является сильным стрессом и приносит в жизнь будущей мамы некоторый дискомфорт, связанный с изменениями в ее теле и ростом ребенка.

Ключевые слова: боль в спине, беременность, женщины, грыжа, репродуктивный возраст

Камалова Дилафруз Дониоровна
Норхо'жайева Чаросхон Бобир қизи
Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti

HOMILADORLIK PAYTIDAGI BEL OG'RIG'I (ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI)

ANNOTATSIYA

Homiladorlik paytida bel og'rig'i: paydo bo'lish sabablari, qanday kasalliklar, tashxis va davolash usullari. Bel og'rig'i homilador ayollarning antenatal klinikada, ayniqsa keyingi bosqichlarda qabul qilishda eng ko'p uchraydigan shikoyatlaridan biridir. Homiladorlik tabiiy jarayon bo'lsa-da, ayolning tanasi uchun bu juda stressli va kelajakdagi onaning hayotiga uning tanasidagi o'zgarishlar va bolaning o'sishi bilan bog'liq ba'zi noqulayliklarni keltirib chiqaradi.

Kalit so'zlar: bel og'rig'i, homiladorlik, ayollar, churra, reproductiv yosh

Introduction. Back pain leads to restriction of activity of the future mum and disruption of the usual way of life. Sometimes back pain is a symptom that requires urgent medical attention. Often during pregnancy, women are faced with pain in the lower back. In most cases, it is caused by musculoskeletal causes - overstrain of ligaments and muscles, intervertebral protrusions and hernias. But also back pain in pregnancy can signal the pathology of internal organs, including female genital organs. In this period of a woman's life, the list of available diagnostic procedures is very narrow and not all the usual ways of treatment are possible[1]. In the article we will pay attention to the problem of why the lower back hurts in early pregnancy. We will talk about the causes, possible methods of diagnosis and treatment, as well as pay special attention to the symptoms that should alert both the future mother and the attending physician. Prevention of back pain in pregnant women is reduced to maintaining the correct position of the body,

regular exercise, massage on the advice of a doctor and wearing supportive belts[2].

During pregnancy, the female body is subjected to a specific load, especially the spine. Therefore, the most common problem is back pain. During pregnancy, a woman's weight can increase up to 16-20kg, which leads to changes in posture. In addition, the cause of back pain can be hormonal changes[3]. During this period, relaxin is more actively produced, which is responsible for the elasticity of muscles and stretchability of ligaments. It contributes to easy childbirth, but during pregnancy leads to excessive mobility of joints and ligaments. During pregnancy, all the diseases that were earlier aggravated. And, as we know, after 30 years of age, it is rare to meet a person with a healthy back[4].

During pregnancy, biochemical, hormonal, functional and anatomical changes begin in all organ systems of the future mother.

There is a physiological adaptation of the organism to the upcoming carrying of the child and childbirth. In addition to external and internal genital organs, glands of internal secretion, pronounced metamorphosis is subjected and musculoskeletal system. Against the background of redistribution of the load on the ligaments and muscles can occur pain in the lower back in the first weeks of pregnancy[5]. The most common reason why pregnancy back pain in the first, second, and especially in the third trimester, is physiological restructuring. Gradually increasing body weight of a woman entails a redistribution of the load on the vertebrae and intervertebral discs of the lumbosacral spine, hip joints. Due to the growing uterus and abdomen, the centre of gravity shifts: the lumbar lordosis increases - the spinal column bends more strongly to the front. And the pelvis tilts forwards, which helps to stretch the abdominal muscles. Additional strain is placed on the periorbital muscles at the lumbar level. Accordingly, the tone of the muscles changes[6].

Another factor in the development of musculoskeletal pain in pregnancy is a change in the hormonal background of a woman. In particular, the production of a large amount of the hormone relaxin leads to excessive relaxation of muscles and stretching of ligaments[7].

We can distinguish types of back pain depending on the term of pregnancy: early term pain and late term pain. According to their characteristics, the pain can be aching, pulling, shooting.

Back pain in pregnancy occurs more often in the lumbar spine, but can also be localised in other parts of the spine: cervical, thoracic, sacrococcygeal [8].

There are risk factors that are not one hundred per cent, but are very likely to provoke moderate or severe low back pain in pregnancy:

- High body mass index of the mother;
- frequent intense physical exertion;
- sedentary lifestyle;
- history of spinal diseases of degenerative-dystrophic genesis;
- late reproductive age
- regular stress

In late pregnancy, usually closer to 38-42 weeks, a woman may be bothered by preliminaries - periodic pulling pains in the lower back and abdomen. Often these are 'training contractions', which do not indicate the beginning of labour activity and do not pose a danger in terms of the development of spinal disorders.

Pathological back pain during pregnancy, the cause of which can be a threat of miscarriage and premature labour, are dangerous conditions for the life of the woman and the future child. They are accompanied by bloody discharge from the genital tract, abdominal pain, especially in the lower part of the abdomen, a feeling of distention in the vagina, the symptoms may resemble contractions or pronounced pain during menstruation.

Let us list the main pathological conditions in which patients complain of lower back pain when walking in pregnancy:

- pyelonephritis
- glomerulonephritis
- intervertebral hernia
- urolithiasis
- pancreatitis
- threat of pregnancy termination due to uterine and ovarian pathology

Sharp pronounced pain in the back in combination with vaginal discharge, increased body temperature or changes in the colour and transparency of urine should alert a woman - urgently seek medical help from an obstetrician-gynecologist. If the pain goes to the lower extremities, accompanied by numbness or muscle weakness in them, as well as disorders of the function of the pelvic organs, it is necessary to consult a neurologist. After all, this may signal an intervertebral hernia, compressing the nerve root. In all these conditions, you need to get a doctor's consultation and specialised treatment [9].

Back pain during pregnancy occurs for various reasons. Conventionally, we can talk about physiological causes of back pain, although it is worth noting that normally pregnancy goes on without pain until late in pregnancy, and the appearance of painful sensations should be reported to your doctor. The lumbosacral spine in women during pregnancy experiences increasing stresses. So-called physiological pain can occur late in pregnancy due to a shift in the centre

of gravity of the body, overloading of the lumbar muscles and compression of organs and nerve plexuses by the enlarged uterus.

Often such pains occur in multiple pregnancies and when the foetus is large. The hormonal background of a woman undergoes significant changes during pregnancy. A large amount of the hormone relaxin is produced, which contributes to muscle relaxation, stretching of ligaments, which in turn leads to joint instability and pain. At the end of pregnancy, there may be so-called preliminarian pains - irregular pulling pains in the lower abdomen, lower back, sacrum. Such pains are harbingers of labour. They are also called 'training contractions', while the general condition of the future mother is not disturbed, sleep is preserved[10].

Pathological back pain during pregnancy, the cause of which may be a threat of miscarriage and premature labour, are dangerous conditions for the life of the woman and the future child. They are accompanied by abdominal pain, especially in the lower part of the abdomen, a feeling of distention in the vagina (they may resemble contractions or pronounced pain during menstruation), bloody discharge from the genital tract[8].

Any back pain in a pregnant woman should be differentiated with gestational pyelonephritis (inflammation of the kidney pelvis during pregnancy). The disease begins with a rise in temperature to high values, chills, pain in the lumbar region, nausea, sometimes vomiting. Women with urolithiasis may experience an attack of renal colic - intense pain in the lower back, radiating to the perineum, blood may appear in the urine. However, painless spontaneous discharge of stones is also possible. As a result of impaired urine outflow, kidney malfunction occurs, and with prolonged blockage of the stone may occur irreversible changes in the structure of the kidney with its gradual shriveling or inflammation. Pain of a shingles characteristic of pancreatitis. Such pain is accompanied by loss of appetite, aversion to fatty foods, attacks of nausea and vomiting, rumbling in the abdomen, diarrhea[4].

Chronic cholecystitis can bring a lot of discomfort to the life of a pregnant woman: a bitter taste in the mouth, pain in the right subcostal and lower back, a feeling of heaviness. The exacerbation of the disease is accompanied by a slight rise in temperature[2].

Often such pains occur in multiple pregnancies and when the foetus is large. The hormonal background of a woman undergoes significant changes during pregnancy. A large amount of the hormone relaxin is produced, which contributes to muscle relaxation, stretching of ligaments, which in turn leads to joint instability and pain. At the end of pregnancy, there may be so-called preliminarian pains - irregular pulling pains in the lower abdomen, lower back, sacrum. Such pains are harbingers of labour. They are also called 'training contractions', while the general condition of the future mother is not disturbed, sleep is preserved[6].

Pathological back pain during pregnancy, the cause of which may be a threat of miscarriage and premature labour, are dangerous conditions for the life of the woman and the future child. They are accompanied by abdominal pain, especially in the lower part of the abdomen, a feeling of distention in the vagina (they may resemble contractions or pronounced pain during menstruation), bloody discharge from the genital tract[3].

Any back pain in a pregnant woman should be differentiated with gestational pyelonephritis (inflammation of the kidney pelvis during pregnancy). The disease begins with a rise in temperature to high values, chills, pain in the lumbar region, nausea, sometimes vomiting. Women with urolithiasis may experience an attack of renal colic - intense pain in the lower back, radiating to the perineum, blood may appear in the urine. However, painless spontaneous discharge of stones is also possible. As a result of impaired urine outflow, kidney malfunction occurs, and with prolonged blockage of the stone may occur irreversible changes in the structure of the kidney with its gradual shriveling or inflammation [1].

Conclusions: Thus, pain of a shingles characteristic of pancreatitis. Such pain is accompanied by loss of appetite, aversion to fatty foods, attacks of nausea and vomiting, rumbling in the abdomen, diarrhea. Chronic cholecystitis can bring a lot of discomfort to the life of a pregnant woman: a bitter taste in the mouth, pain in the right subcostal

and lower back, a feeling of heaviness. The exacerbation of the disease is accompanied by a slight rise in temperature.

Literature

1. Кузьминов К.О., Бахтадзе М.А. Болотов Д.А. и др. Опыт использования опросников для оценки болевого синдрома у больных с радикулопатией поясничной локализации // Мануальная терапия. - 2014; 1: 11-6.
2. Гайнуллин И.Р. и др. Клиническая оценка влияния остеопатического сопровождения беременных на процесс родоразрешения // Российский остеопатический журнал. - 2017; 1-2: 47-52.
3. Садовская Ю.О., Мишина С.В. Возможности остеопатии в комплексной профилактике фетоплацентарной недостаточности у беременных женщин // Российский остеопатический журнал. - 2016; 1-2: 22-8.
4. Адизов С.Р., Жиемуратова Г.К., Алламурастов К.Е. Остеохондроз и грыжа диска позвоночника у беременных женщин и их влияние на течение и исходы беременности. Сб. ст. междунаучно-практ. конф. «Роль и место информационных технологий в современной науке» / Казань, 2017; с. 96-8.
5. Ваганова Я.А. и др. Эффективность применения методов медицинской реабилитации во время беременности, с целью купирования болевого синдрома в спине, вызванного дорсопатиями // Современные проблемы науки и образования. - 2016; 6: 240.
6. Животов В.А., Радченко О.А. Способ восстановления и оздоровления пациента с использованием балансировки мышечно-фасциально-висцеральных цепей подходом через основание черепа. Патент на изобретение С12611908RU. М., 2015; 17 с.
7. Федоров Д.В., Егорова А.Т. Опыт лечения болевого синдрома у беременных мягкими техниками мануальной терапии. Тез. докл. XII научно-практ. конф. «Актуальные вопросы медицинской реабилитации: инновационные технологии, клиническое питание, традиционные аспекты» / Новосибирск, 2017; с. 121-5.
8. Sheraton A., Streckfuss J., Grace S. Experiences of pregnant women receiving osteopathic care // J. Bodyw. Mov. Ther. - 2018; 22 (2): 321-7. DOI: 10.1016/j.jbmt.2017.09.007
9. McGlone F. et al. The role of gentle touch in perinatal osteopathic manual therapy // Neurosci. Biobehavioral Rev. - 2017; 72: 1-9.
10. Franke H. et al. Osteopathic manipulative treatment for low back and pelvic girdle pain during and after pregnancy: A systematic review and meta-analysis // J. Bodyw. Mov. Ther. - 2017; 21 (4): 752-62.

ЖУРНАЛ НЕВРОЛОГИИ И НЕЙРОХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 2

JOURNAL OF NEUROLOGY AND NEUROSURGERY RESEARCH

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 2

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Тадqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000